

Co-UDlabs

Building Collaborative Urban Drainage
research labs communities

D2.5. Appendix D – Survey Distribution and Data Collection Process

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1. Executive summary of the activities for the Co-UDLabs Task2.3

1.1. Adaptation to different realities

The survey was adapted to fit different national contexts to ensure relevance and clarity for stakeholders across various countries. Recognizing that wastewater management practices, regulatory frameworks, and organizational structures vary across Europe, the survey design was tailored to reflect these differences in terminology, policy focus, and operational priorities.

For example, in Germany, the survey was pre-tested with industry partners to gauge its appropriateness for local wastewater associations, municipalities, and public drainage operators (See Section 5). This pre-testing process allowed the survey to be fine-tuned based on direct feedback from practitioners, helping to ensure that questions were aligned with the practical realities and challenges specific to the German wastewater sector. Additionally, adjustments were made to accommodate specific regulations, reporting standards, and organizational responsibilities within Germany's public wastewater systems.

For other countries, similar adaptations were made based on national priorities and operational standards. For instance, the survey language was translated and nuanced to fit the administrative and regulatory language used in Belgium, the Netherlands, and the UK, enhancing accessibility and relevance for local operators. By customizing content to align with each country's wastewater management practices, the survey was able to capture a more accurate and representative range of responses across the European wastewater sector.

During the adaptation process, it became clear that the Swiss context for wastewater management was not easily transferable to other countries. Previously unrecognized, this difference highlighted that Switzerland's unique regulatory structures, where wastewater disposal is organized by local or regional associations ("Abwasserzweckverband"), and operational practices did not align closely with those in other European countries. As a result, some Swiss-specific survey elements were deemed incompatible with other national contexts by the partners.

Despite this discovery, the decision was made to proceed with the survey rollout, adjusting only where absolutely necessary and focusing on capturing a broader range of insights applicable across diverse regulatory and operational environments. This approach allowed the survey to maintain its relevance while acknowledging that the Swiss model might present certain limitations in comparability.

1.2. Roll-out of the survey

Based on the good experiences with the previous survey (Manny_2018), we decided to roll out the survey via national and international interest groups or associations, e.g. EWA, GRAIE, etc. who would notify their members

(data protection: we do not want to collect personal information). The WP2 core group decided that GRAIE was officially mentioned as contact for the survey.

The survey was first launched at the on June 10 2024 at the International Conference of Urban Drainage (ICUD) conference in Delft, where Wendy Francken (Managing Director of VLARIO, Belgium; Current president of EWA, Former chairwoman of EWA European Policy Committee) was contacted by Eawag and USFD and agreed to promote the survey with their members. An online meeting was scheduled for Wed 18 Sept 2024 to discuss intermediate results and further distribution of final results. Recommendation i) to organize reality check with industry professionals from selected utilities, interest to discuss results at annual EWA meeting.

To facilitate access and promote transparency, the Co-UDlabs team published a dedicated webpage titled "Unveiling the Flow: A Co-UDLabs Survey on Monitoring Combined Sewer Overflows (CSOs)." (Figure 1). The webpage hosted the survey in multiple languages and included an outline of survey objectives, target audience, and a brief on the importance of monitoring CSOs across Europe.

Following the announcement in the Co-UDlabs newsletter on June 18, 2024, which introduced the survey alongside other project updates, the link to the survey was distributed via the online portal LinkedIn and Twitter.com. Following this, a coordinated series of steps unfolded to ensure broad reach and participation from relevant stakeholders across different European countries (See Appendix D).

In September 2024 the survey deadline was extended due to low response rates in partner countries outside Switzerland (Figure 2). Partners like the European Water Association (EWA) joined in promoting the survey with an email sent out to their members on September 10. EWA committed to circulating the survey link among its members and sent a follow-up email on September 23. Personal contacts in Germany first agreed to promote the survey through DWA in Baden-Württemberg, but later declined the distribution because they feared that it would interfere with a survey of their own. In September the survey was also shared with the members of the Urban Drainage committee of the Spanish Association of Water Supply and Wastewater Operators (AEAS). We also send the survey to Eureau through the member of Eureau in our International Advisory Board, but apparently it was not shared within the members of the association.

In October 2024 the survey deadline was extended a second time and then closed on 31.10.2024.

The screenshot shows the Co-UDlabs homepage with a prominent blue banner for the survey. The banner text is: "Unveiling the Flow: A Co-UDLabs survey on monitoring combined sewer overflows (CSOs)". Below the banner, there is a sub-heading: "A survey on the current state of CSO monitoring and performance assessment in Europe". To the right of the banner, there are several QR codes, each with a small image and text in a different language: English, Danish, Dutch, German, and Spanish. Below the QR codes, there is a "References" section with two entries. At the bottom of the page, there are social media sharing icons (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn) and a "Category" section listing "General news, Networking" and "Publication date: 10 June 2024".

Figure 1 The survey was published on the CoUDlabs homepage on June 10 2024.

The image shows two social media posts. The left post is from LinkedIn, posted by 'Co-UDlabs - Building Collaborative Urban Drainage research labs...' with 573 followers. The post text is: "Answer the Co-UDlabs survey on monitoring combined sewer overflows (CSOs)!" followed by a link "https://lnkd.in/emnHz3PC ...more". The post includes a small image of a survey form and a bar chart titled "What motivates operators?". The right post is from Twitter, posted by Jörg Rieckermann, a researcher at Urban Water Management, Eawag. The post text is: "Help Shape the Future of Urban Drainage!" followed by "Our Co-UDlabs survey on CSO Monitoring is uncovering key insights into how different countries manage Combined Sewer Overflows. But we need your input to get the full picture!". The post also includes a small image of a survey form and a bar chart titled "What motivates operators?".

Figure 2 the survey was distributed through email, professional networks, e.g. Komnet (IKT) and social media, e.g. LinkedIn and Twitter.

2. DENMARK (AaU)

2.1. What method(s) were used to distribute the survey?

The survey was distributed through the Danish Water and Wastewater Association (DANVA) via its professional networks for drainage managers and practitioners. DANVA is the industry organization for Danish water and wastewater utility companies. Additionally, the survey was sent directly to the largest Danish utility companies, who also distributed it in their professional networks.

2.2. How was the survey tailored to different national contexts?

The survey was translated into Danish by the AAU team and adapted to the structure of Danish wastewater services, as well as local legal terminology, ensuring its relevance and clarity for the target audience as best as possible.

2.3. What timeline was followed for the survey rollout?

The survey was distributed in September, deliberately scheduled to avoid the summer months of July and August, when many people are on holiday. This timing was chosen to prevent the survey from being overlooked or forgotten, ensuring better engagement once the holiday season had concluded.

2.4. How did you ensure a high response rate?

The credibility of the survey was sought to be ensured through DANVA's professional networks and the AAU team's personal contacts.

2.5. What challenges were encountered, and how were they addressed?

The main challenge has been adapting the survey for use across Europe, ensuring it remains true to the original Swiss questionnaire while also making it accurate and relevant in the Danish context.

3. England and Wales (UoS)

3.1. What method(s) were used to distribute the survey?

The survey was not distributed in England and Wales. This is because comprehensive and publicly accessible data on CSOs already exists in these countries.

In England and Wales, combined sewer overflow performance data is widely collected and open to the public. Combined sewer overflows are defined as ‘Storm Overflows’, and the dataset is known as the ‘Event Duration Monitoring - Storm Overflows - Annual Returns’ dataset.

The goal of the CoUDlabs survey was to understand what performance data is available at utilities, for which purpose these data are used, and the motivation of stakeholder to publish performance indicators on CSOs.

As described in section 2.4 in the deliverable D2.5, this data is already available for England and Wales, hence the survey was not circulated. The questionnaire was however scrutinized for the English situation, which highlighted challenges in rolling out a comparable questionnaire in different European countries.

In England and Wales, the EWA also requested that the wastewater operators support the survey distribution, though it remains unclear if or how they proceeded with this.

3.2. How was the survey tailored to different national contexts?

We engaged in the translation and voiced concern that it would be not reasonable to adjust the survey to the reality in the UK. For example, there do not even exist municipalities in the strict sense and the wastewater systems are all managed by private entities. For details, see Section 3.5. below.

3.3. What timeline was followed for the survey rollout?

As the data were already available, and the legal chain in place, we opted not to roll out the survey.

3.4. How did you ensure a high response rate?

In the UK, as there are no specific municipal organizations involved, we would have suggested to roll out the study through personal contacts within wastewater companies and network operators.

3.5. What challenges were encountered, and how were they addressed?

When adapting and translating the original Swiss CSO questionnaire by Manny et al. (2018) for rolling out in the rest of Europe, it became clear that having a questionnaire where the questions are consistent such that results are comparable, but also phrasing and translating the questions so that they are understood in the different countries was challenging.

For example, the original questionnaire asked ‘how many communities or municipalities are served by your organisation’, and ‘how do you assess the operational freedoms of your organisation vis-à-vis the municipalities’. **However, in England, there are no municipalities.** In many parts of England there are 2 tiers of local government: 1. county councils and 2. district, borough or city councils. In some parts of the country, there’s just 1 (unitary) tier of local government providing all the local services, of which the 3 main types are: unitary authorities in shire areas, London boroughs or metropolitan boroughs (UK Government, 2024b). In Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland, it works differently again (UK Government, 2024b). In England, the Water Companies are privatised and regulated by the Water Services Regulation Authority (OFWAT) and Environment Agency.

4. France (GRAIE)

4.1. What method(s) were used to distribute the survey?

In France, the survey was rolled out through the members of GRAIE (Groupe de Réflexion et d'Action pour l'Innovation dans l'Eau), a prominent association that brings together professionals and organizations involved in water management and innovation. GRAIE's members include municipalities, water utilities, and industry experts, making it an ideal network for reaching stakeholders in the field of wastewater management.

4.2. How was the survey tailored to different national contexts?

The survey was tailored to the French context by partnering with GRAIE, which has substantial experience with surveys in the French wastewater sector. Although this provided an almost ideal platform for reaching the French wastewater sector, the survey could have also been shared through Astee, a broader network in the sector, with some adjustments made to the questions to better align with the specific needs of the French audience. This would ensure that the survey was more suited to the local context and focused on the most pertinent issues for respondents in France.

4.3. What timeline was followed for the survey rollout?

The survey roll-out took place in September, carefully timed to avoid the summer months of July and August, when many in France are on holiday. Distributing the survey during this period ensured it would not be overlooked or forgotten, as it allowed for better engagement once the holiday season had ended.

4.4. How did you ensure a high response rate?

To ensure a high response rate, we benefitted from Graie's strong credibility within the French wastewater sector. As a trusted organization, Graie's involvement in the survey distribution encouraged greater participation and confidence from the target audience. Their reputation should have helped increase the survey's visibility and reinforced its legitimacy.

4.5. What challenges were encountered, and how were they addressed?

Unfortunately, the response rate was unsatisfactory. Given the timeframe and constraints, issuing follow-up emails and offering incentives were not really feasible. However, the use of Graie’s credibility played a significant role in encouraging participation, as their endorsement helped ensure the survey was taken seriously by the target audience.

5. Germany (IKT)

5.1. What method(s) were used to distribute the survey?

The partners chose to distribute the survey through IKT's network association, KomNetABWASSER. On September 9, 2024, an email with the survey was sent to approximately 180 municipalities and wastewater associations in Germany that are members of KomNetABWASSER, along with over 2,000 non-members across the country (see KomNetABWASSER). The survey was further shared with Belgian, British, and Dutch municipalities, water companies, and network operators during IKT's international conference, "Sewers for the 21st Century – II 2024," held on September 11 in Gelsenkirchen. Distribution at the event included organizations such as Gemeente Arnhem, Gemeente Nijmegen, Gemeente Rotterdam, Gemeente Capelle aan den IJssel (Netherlands); Fluvius, Fary, and Vivaqua (Belgium); and Isle Utilities, Yorkshire Water, and Wessex Water (UK).

In Germany, the EWA also requested that DWA support survey distribution, though it remains unclear if or how DWA proceeded with this.

5.2. How was the survey tailored to different national contexts?

In Germany, the survey was pre-tested with public wastewater companies (Municipalities) e.g. city of Warendorf, in personal interviews to gauge its appropriateness for local wastewater associations, municipalities, and public drainage operators. This pre-testing process allowed the survey to be fine-tuned based on direct feedback from practitioners, helping to ensure that questions were aligned with the practical realities and challenges specific to the German wastewater sector. Additionally, adjustments were made to accommodate specific regulations, reporting standards, and organizational responsibilities within Germany's public wastewater systems.

5.3. What timeline was followed for the survey rollout?

The survey was distributed via email to the municipal network of wastewater operators on 09.09.2024.

The email with PDF attachment was sent to approx. 180 Municipalities or Wastewater Operators in Germany, which are member of IKT's network association KomNetABWASSER¹ and to more than 2,000 non-members in Germany. It was also announced in their online event "Abwassersprechstunde" in the same week, on 13.09.

Furthermore, a flyer was distributed to the European participants on IKT's International Conference "Sewers for the 21st Century – II 2024" on the 11th of September at IKT, Gelsenkirchen. This included participants from Belgian,

¹ <https://www.komnetabwasser.de/>

British and Dutch Municipalities, Water Companies and Network Operators. Finally, the survey documents were also distributed to individual stakeholders: Gemeente Arnhem (NL), Gemeente Nijmegen (NL), Gemeente Rotterdam (NL), Gemeente Capelle aan den IJssel (NL), Fluvius (B), Fary (B), Vivaqua (B), Isle Utilities (UK), Yorkshire Water (UK) and Wessex Water (UK).

5.4. How did you ensure a high response rate?

This timeline described above ensured a high response rate by utilizing multiple channels to reach the target audience. Distributing the survey via email to the municipal network of wastewater operators on 09.09.2024 provided direct access to the key participants. Additionally, announcing the survey at the online event “Abwassersprechstunde” on 13.09.2024 allowed for real-time engagement and visibility. The flyer distribution at the IKT event on 10.-11.09.2024 further expanded the survey's reach to a wider European audience, ensuring maximum exposure and increasing the likelihood of a high response rate.

5.5. What challenges were encountered, and how were they addressed?

Unfortunately, despite the considerable effort and the high credibility of IKT, the response rate was rather low. To address this, efforts were made to enhance visibility and engagement, including leveraging IKT's credibility and personal contacts. Despite these efforts, the low response rate was likely influenced by timing constraints and other external factors.

The low response rate is probably due to the fact that wastewater companies (Municipalities and water associations) in Germany already have to complete numerous questionnaires and reports as part of their reporting obligations to the authorities (e.g. water authorities, environmental agencies, employers liability insurance association) and to other institutions (e.g. DWA, Federal Statistical Office).

For context: regarding the representativeness of German responses, approximately 6,600 public wastewater system operators exist in Germany, including municipalities, public urban drainage companies, and water associations (source: BDEW/DESTA: Abwasserdaten Deutschland. Strukturdaten der Abwasserentsorgung, 4th updated edition, 2019²).

² https://www.bdew.de/media/documents/Ansicht_bdew_broschuere_abwasserdaten.pdf

6. NETHERLANDS (Deltares)

6.1. What method(s) were used to distribute the survey?

The survey was distributed through the branche organization RIONED via its professional networks for drainage managers and practitioners. In addition, it was sent to contacts in the personal network of the employees involved in Co-UDlabs.

6.2. How was the survey tailored to different national contexts?

The survey was translated into Dutch and as far as possible, tailored to the Dutch context, which differs substantially to the original (Swiss) perspective on which the original versions was based). Given the different legal systems, in some cases this proved to be not possible.

6.3. What timeline was followed for the survey rollout?

The survey was distributed in September and 4 weeks time was offered to fill out, as expected no response, as the survey was one of the many circulating in the professional field,

6.4. How did you ensure a high response rate?

We tried to translate the original survey as good as possible to the Dutch situation, which was complex, as the regulation systems in the Netherlands differs substantially from that in Switzerland, on top of that regulations have undergone changes due to the new 'Omgevingswet' (Environmental Law) which was introduced on 1/1/2024

6.5. What challenges were encountered, and how were they addressed?

As explained before: there were many challenges (recent changes in the legislation, different metrics in the legislation when compared to the original Swiss perspective of the survey, a certain 'survey-fatigue' in the professional field). The main action taken to mitigate these challenges was to make a translation as good as possible. In spite of this, no response was obtained.

7. SPAIN (UDC)

7.1. What method(s) were used to distribute the survey?

In Spain the survey was presented at the national congress of the AEAS (Spanish Association of water supply and wastewater operators) in early June. After the presentation, the UDC contacted with the AEAS Urban Drainage Committee board to roll out the survey among the representatives of the committee (about 100 participants including water utilities, operators, industry partners, national and river catchment authorities, and also some universities). The survey was delivered to the members of the committee by the end of September.

Besides rolling out the survey through the wastewater association, UDC members also send emails informing about the survey to their internal network. The project coordinator reposted some official entry of Co-UDlabs informing about the survey in his social networks. Lastly, the survey was also presented to the 20 participants of the Urban Drainage Metrology Course organized by UDC in July 2025.

7.2. How was the survey tailored to different national contexts?

The survey was translated into Spanish by UDC team and adapted to Spanish wastewater services structure and legal terminology of some definitions like CSO. After the adaptation, all the questions of the survey make sense for the Spanish context although some of the options of a few enquiries were not allowable within the Spanish organizational structure (e.g. in Spain the network owner is always a public administration, company or intercommunal association of different water users (e.g. municipalities).

7.3. What timeline was followed for the survey rollout?

In summary, the timeline was:

- Presentation at AEAS congress, Castellón – early June
- Presentation at CO-UDlabs Urban drainage metrology course participants in A Coruña – mid July
- Mailing to UDC internal network – early September
- Mailing to AEAS representatives on Urban Drainage Committee – late September.

7.4. How did you ensure a high response rate?

In Spain we tried to have a high response rate by presenting by rolling out the survey through the Spanish operator's association AEAS. We also tried to engage participants by direct email and phone calls to a few large water operators. We tried to emphasize the importance of the survey and as it is well aligned and connected with the last updates of the national level Spanish regulations of CSO. Thus, in July 2023 a new regulation was released by the Spanish central government related with the control of CSO spills and the sizing of CSO structures. In the new regulation monitoring of CSO structures is mandatory for urban communities larger than 50.000 p.e.

7.5. What challenges were encountered, and how were they addressed?

The perception of the UDC regarding the challenges of gathering responses for the survey is that at Spanish level, water utilities are really cautious and are not in favor of providing public information about the overall management of the Urban Drainage Systems or making their data of CSO spill open. Furthermore, since the end of 2023, the Urban Drainage Community (e.g. the Urban Drainage Committee of AEAS) is on big debate about how to fulfil the new requirements of the new regulations approved by the national government. A specific working group on the analysis of the new regulation is testing the new requirements in different Spanish catchment with the aim of providing some recommendations to the government. Thus, right now the timing is not really optimum as water operators are afraid of sharing more information than the strictly needed.

By the other hand, the Spanish water administration is split in national level and regional level water authorities. The monitoring and reporting requirements are not homogenous, even at the same political region in which more than one river authority could have water competences.